

Technical report on policy integration mechanisms and gaps for the implementation of integrated conservation planning in Europe

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1. Introduction

The continued loss of global biodiversity presents a threat to the security of our society, health, environment and economies. So far attempts to halt and reverse the trends of biodiversity loss have largely failed with biodiversity “declining in all regions of the world and at all spatial scales” (IPBES, 2024). Protection, preservation and restoration of biodiversity requires a cross-realm approach linking terrestrial, freshwater and marine ecosystems (Hermoso et al. 2021; Álvarez-Romero et al. 2015). This approach of integrated spatial planning identifies that those activities undertaken in one realm impact another and that the interactions between realms must be considered and understood (Ballantyne et al. 2024, Leontiou et al. 2022, Threlfall et al. 2021).

This too is the case within the European Union (EU), and it is essential that connectivity and the importance of cross-realm effects are not overlooked in the EU policy mix. Previous iterations of the EU Biodiversity Strategy (BDS) have failed to cease the trend of European biodiversity loss, but the European Green Deal (EGD) aims to integrate biodiversity conservation across EU policy to change this (Jung et al. 2024; Hermoso et al. 2022; EEA. 2020). Under the EGD, the EU environmental policy mix has grown and diversified with a range of new and amended Directives, Regulations and Strategies covering key areas and sectors such as food, water, energy, nature restoration, human health and economy. The EGD states that “all EU policies should contribute to preserving and restoring Europe’s natural capital” (European Commission. 2019). This principle of policy integration is not new and has been incorporated since the adoption of the Single European Act in 1986, however, the EGD represents an ambitious new strategy for integrating economy, society and the environment that moves away from the traditional sectoral approach (Biedenkopf & Delreux. 2023).

This technical report presents the findings of the Biodiversa+ INSPIRE project on cross-realm policy integration mechanisms, gaps for the implementation of integrated conservation planning in Europe and future research.

2. Methodology

2.1. Data Sources

To investigate the scope of the policy documents within the EU environmental policy mix, focused on biodiversity conservation, an internet-based search was conducted for all relevant EU Directives, Regulations, Strategies, Action Plans, Initiatives and Missions. A number of sources were identified to investigate the breadth of relevant policy documents:

- EU-Central Asia Water, Environment and Climate Change Cooperation (WECOOP) knowledge centre on EU Environment Policy (<https://wecoop.eu/regional-knowledge-centre/eu-policies-regulations/>)
- European Commission ‘Energy, Climate Change, Environment’ website ‘Topics’ resource on EU Policy (https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics_en)
- European Commission ‘The European Green Deal’ website ‘What we are working on’ resource (https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en)
- European Commission ‘EU Biodiversity Strategy Actions Tracker’ (<https://dopa.jrc.ec.europa.eu/kcbd/actions-tracker/>)

The 41 policy documents identified for analysis were categorized into terrestrial (n=10, 25.4%), marine (n=6, 14.6%), water (n=7, 17.1%) and multiple-realm (n=18, 43.9%). The characterisation and timeline of chosen policy documents can be observed in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Timeline of EU policy documents chosen for analysis

3. Integration Mechanisms

Integration mechanisms within policy documents address cross-realm and cross-sector dependencies. Examples of mechanisms include simple static references to other policy documents or more dynamic if-then conditions that relate the provisions for one realm or sector to the conditions in another. The mechanisms for policy integration to meet the needs of conservation at the crossroads of terrestrial, freshwater, and marine realms can be determined as static references.

The analysis demonstrated that the European Green Deal (EGD) and EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (BDS) are key connectors to the smaller communities observable in the network alongside the key single realm policy documents of the Water Framework Directive (WFD, freshwater), Common Agricultural Policy (CAP, terrestrial) and Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD, marine). Further analysis demonstrated that the most important policy documents (based on the quality of their connections to other important policy documents) again included EGD, BDS, WFD and CAP with the inclusion of the Nature Directives (Habitats and Birds Directives). The MSFD was found to be of lower importance and was exceeded by the food system policy documents of the Farm to Fork Strategy and Common Fisheries Policy. A potential reason for this relates to the drivers of biodiversity loss outlined in Jaureguiberry (2022) and IPBES (2019) and indicates the requirement for further study on the dynamic if-then mechanisms related to cross-sector dependencies.

4. Gaps to Implementation and Further research

Studies have found that the main drivers of biodiversity loss differ for each realm (Jaureguiberry, 2022 and IPBES, 2019): Terrestrial realm biodiversity loss is driven by land use change and direct exploitation of resources related to intensive management for cropping and animal husbandry. In the freshwater realm, land use change related to intensive agriculture and pollution are the main drivers of loss. The marine realm suffers biodiversity loss, direct exploitation of resources related to overfishing and to lesser degrees climate change and pollution.

These findings are echoed in the structure of the policy network map with observable communities linked to land use, food systems and pollution. This all points to the requirement for an integrated approach, encapsulating all realms to create more sustainable food systems which in turn reduce pollution. A study undertaken on the implementation of biodiversity strategies found that the agricultural sector was attributed as the main driver of biodiversity loss in all its case study countries (Cardrona Santos et al. 2023). It is clear from the analysis undertaken in this study that food systems related to fishing and terrestrial agriculture are key components of the EU policy mix. Therefore, the success of the objectives laid out in the BDS and EGD rely heavily on how well all policy instruments are integrated and coordinated with across realms and in relation to the food system sectors.

The synergy of environmental and agricultural objectives across differing policy instruments can be difficult to achieve as these policies address differing issues and their implementation approaches are dissimilar in the sense that environmental policies are often regulatory instruments and agricultural policies subsidy based (Bazzan, 2023). An example of this lies in the freshwater realm with the implementation of the WFD which trades off water resource protection against CAP goals related to intensified production (Schaub, 2022).

Further research is planned to better understand the cross-sectoral policy integration mechanisms. The importance of creating integration of cross-sector policies to manage cross-realm issues is well understood in the literature (Metz et al. 2020) and so the INSPIRE project aims to develop a typology of integration mechanism to address this.

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